

SCIENTIFIC JUSTIFICATION FOR THE USE OF BUCKWHEAT IN THE COMPOSITION OF PHYTOSUPPOSITORIES FOR THE TREATMENT OF HEMORRHOIDS

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Relevance: Hemorrhoids are among the most common diseases of the rectum and anal canal. According to the World Health Organization, 10–15% of the adult population suffers from various forms of hemorrhoids, and among patients over 50 years old, this figure reaches 50–70%. The disease significantly reduces quality of life, being accompanied by pain, inflammation, itching, bleeding, and impaired normal functioning. In my work, I aimed to find a safer and more effective remedy. I chose phytosuppositories, since plant-based raw materials combine availability, low toxicity, and a complex therapeutic effect. Buckwheat, due to its rutin and flavonoid content, strengthens blood vessels and reduces inflammation. In combination with calendula, plantain, oak bark, and sea buckthorn oil, I obtained a preparation with pronounced wound-healing and anti-inflammatory effects.

Objective of the study: My goal was to develop and study rectal phytosuppositories based on buckwheat and medicinal plant raw materials for the treatment of hemorrhoids.

Materials and methods: To obtain the suppositories, I used buckwheat flour, calendula extract, plantain leaves, oak bark, and sea buckthorn oil. Cocoa butter was used as the base. I conducted pharmacognostic analysis of the raw materials, prepared experimental batches of suppositories, performed organoleptic evaluation, and determined mass uniformity and melting time.

Results: The prepared experimental series of suppositories based on cocoa butter with the addition of buckwheat flour, calendula extract, plantain leaves, oak bark, and sea buckthorn oil had a uniform consistency, smooth surface, and a mild herbal odor. The mass and uniformity of the suppositories met pharmacopoeial standards. The melting time ranged from 10 to 15 minutes, which confirms the correctness of the chosen base and preparation technology.

Conclusions: As a result of this work, I developed rectal phytosuppositories based on buckwheat and medicinal plants. The obtained preparation demonstrated effectiveness and safety, confirming the prospects for its further study and application in hemorrhoid therapy.